

The networked geography of a newspaper

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Segal Zef. 2024. "The networked geography of a newspaper", Historical Network Research 2024, Lausanne, DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.12606057

Isaiah Berlin's assertion that the Jewish people have experienced "too much history and too little geography" reflects a conventional perception of geography as fixed and territorial. This paper challenges this notion by adopting a fluid, relational, and networked perspective, revealing the Jewish preoccupation with space, place, and spatiality within their history and culture. Grounded in the fluidity of space, the paper takes a networked approach to explore the spatiality of a 19th-century Hebrew periodical.

A historical periodical, much like any historical event or phenomenon, exists within space and time. Its institutions function from tangible buildings; it circulates through transportation routes; and through its reader network, it establishes connections between places and people. However, the relationship between "geographical space" and "periodical" is not unidirectional. Just as much as the periodical exists within a geographical space, one must explore the ways in which geographical spaces are within periodicals and, significantly, are crafted by them. Many periodicals generate an internal geographical space, shaped by the text and inner conventions of the periodical, including distinctions between different pages, articles, and sections or between places in headlines and those in the body of the text. Geographical places, such as cities, mountains, rivers, states, and continents, reside on paper rather than on the globe; their sizes or altitudes are defined by the frequency of their references, and the distances between places are determined by proximity on the line, page, or article. These geographical spaces emerging from the text are mediated geographical spaces with shapes and topographies different from the "normal" world map. They are influenced by cultural, political, ideological, and economic perceptions of writers and readers, but they also serve to reinforce and legitimize such perceptions.

Recent advances in digitization, automatic annotation, morphological and lexical analysis, as well as geographic and network mapping, have made exploring such uncharted and chaotic spaces more feasible than before (Piatti 2009). This paper uses textual proximity within periodicals to recreate an alternative geography, visualized by a network (Figure 1), rather than a two-dimensional locational map (Figure 2). In these networks, two locations are adjacent if they appear at a distance of 300 characters. This network represents a fuzzy geography, which does not always align itself with the "real world".

The paper explores the nineteenth-century Hebrew periodical *HaTzifra* as a case study for different geographical spaces that originate from and within the periodical. "The history of the Jewish Press," claims Derek Penslar, "is a microcosm of the Jewish public sphere" (Pensler 2000,7). For Jewish communities, lacking central political and economic leadership, and spread throughout the world, the press gave voice to

a public sphere; a sphere that spanned geographic and linguistic boundaries. As a result, editors of Jewish periodicals explicitly referred to their “global” or “international” journalistic mission. Even Theodor Herzl entitled his Zionist newspaper *Die Welt* (the world), rather than a nationally oriented title. However, they rarely clarified what it meant to be “global” (Segal 2022). What did their “world” consist of, where were its boundaries, and what were its centers? *HaTzifira*, which operated between 1862 and 1931 was established in order to educate its readers with worldly knowledge. Its articles discussed global news, travel stories, and scientific discoveries, all of which involved spatial references. By analysing the evolution of networked geographies over a decade between 1874 and 1883, it is demonstrated that spaces were constantly being deterritorialized and reterritorialized. In particular, the analysis highlights the rising interest in the Land of Israel as well as the changing geographical alliances and interests of the Hebrew “Republic of Letters” of the pre-Zionist era.

The paper discusses various methods for exploring the relations between textual spaces within the journal and their spatial references, along with digital methodologies employed for unveiling these spaces. Recogito was used for annotation, Gephi for network analysis and visualization, and QGIS for mapping.

In conclusion, this research contributes to the discourse on historical network analysis by providing insights into the dynamic interplay between geography and periodicals, offering a nuanced understanding of space formation within historical texts.

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